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Digital method for improved manufacturing of next-generation multifunctional airframe parts

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A STUDY ON CONSOLIDATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES WITH IN-SITU AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESS

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1967 • AIMEN was established with the aims of promoting R&D and high-added value technology services. Industry supported, private centre.

- 2023** • Main technological capabilities in:
- **Advanced Manufacturing**
 - **LASER Processing**
 - Multisectoral Centre
 - International activities in 20 countries
 - Over 750 active customers
 - More than **50 R&D projects per year**
 - Headcount: **280 (50% in R&D&i)**
 - **18 M€** average annual income
 - Over **30 M€** in assets

Location:

- HQ and Laser Processing Centre (O Porriño, Galicia)
- Offices in Madrid

R&D Areas

CONTENT:

✓ **DOMMINIO** PROJECT INTRODUCTION

✓ AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESS: IN-SITU CONSOLIDATION OPTIMIZATION

RESULTS:

- Effect of layup tool temperature
- Effect of compaction roller
- On-going work: laser heating control

✓ CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

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Introduction

DOMMINIO is the acronym of:

‘Digital method for improved manufacturing of next-generation multifunctional airframe parts’

Horizon Europe Topic MG-3-5-2020: ‘Next generation multifunctional and intelligent airframe and engine parts, with emphasis on manufacturing, maintenance and recycling’ (RIA, TRL 2-4)

Call within - Work Programme 2018-2020 Smart, green and integrated transport

Starting Date: First of January 2021

Duration: 42 months (July 2024)

- To enable flexible multistage robotic-based manufacturing production processes
- To develop a Quality-by-Design (QbD) manufacturing strategy.
- To set a data-driven pipeline supporting the design, simulation and production planning.
- To build a combined digital-physical driven methodology for Monitoring and Management of the Health of multifunctional airframe parts.

Introduction

Consortium: 13 partners from 7 countries

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MATERIALS & MANUFACTURING

- Flexible multistage robotic-based production processes
 - ❖ Combining AFP and FFF
 - ❖ cCNT filaments (SHM), CCF and NPs reinforced filaments
- Quality-by-Design (QbD) manufacturing strategy
 - ❖ Laser scanning-assisted heating
 - ❖ FFF nozzle with improved thermal control
 - ❖ Non-contact ultrasound method for in-line

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Demonstrators

Taken from: <https://www.aeroclass.org/spoilers-airplane/>

Taken from: https://raisbeck.com/raisbeck_product/high-flotation-gear-doors/

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Multistage robot-based manufacturing process (AFP + FFF)

1- AFP
Laying up
UD tapes

2- FFF
cCNT reinforced
filaments for SHM

3- AFP
Laying up UD
tapes

4- FFF
a) Filaments reinforced with
MNp's (disassembly)
b) Filaments reinforced with
cCF (structural
reinforcement)

Multifunctional
component

Multistage robot-based manufacturing process (FFF)

▪ FFF robotized pilot cell

- 3D printing head (*high temperature and continuous CF*)
- LASER heating integrated in FFF process.

▪ LFAM cell

- Robotized, CEAD pellets extruder and Typhoon filament extruder.
- Laser heating system.

Multistage robot-based manufacturing process (AFP)

AFP robotized cell:

- Laser diode (6 kW and 4 kW) and VCSEL
- IR heating
- TS, TP and DF materials
- Heated lay-up tool

IR HEATING

LASER HEATING

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- ✓ **AFP (Automated Fibre Placement)** is a very implemented process that have been used for decades in aerospace industry for manufacturing large structures with thermoset composites.
- ✓ **Thermoplastic Composites (TPCs)** offer advantages such as unlimited shelf life at room temperature, recyclability or reprocessability.
- ✓ **LASER assisted In-Situ Consolidation AFP** can contribute to introduce TPCs in aircraft components since is one-step and out-of-autoclave process.
- ✓ **NEED:**
 - To ensure that ISC-AFP obtains the required TPC properties:
⇒ Thermal input during manufacturing vs final material properties

AFP tape

Material: semi-crystalline low melt PAEK thermoplastic matrix and a T800G carbon fibre reinforcement:

Toray Cetex® TC1225 LMPAEK / T800G UD tape

Material properties of matrix.

Material	Tm (°C)	Tg (°C)	Recommended processing temperature by supplier (°C)
LM-PAEK TC1225	305	147	340-385

Composite tape format

Material designation	Fiber Areal Weight, FAW (g/m ²)	Resin content (%)	Ply Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)
TC1225 T800G UD	145	36	0.145	25.4

Raw tape micrograph.

- ✓ AFP (Automated Fibre Placement) head system: PrePro3D model from Conbility manufacturer.
- ✓ The AFP system is mounted in a FANUC R-2000iC/165F Robotic Arm.
- ✓ Heated layup tool. Aluminium alloy plate heated with resistances.
- ✓ Laserline diode laser source (model LDF6000-40) of 6300W and operating wavelengths ranging from 940 to 1060 nm.

Heated lay-up tool

Equipment

AFP parameters

AFP Parameters	Value
Layup speed [mm/s]	100-250
Compaction Max. Force [bar]	6
Temperature [°C]	✓

Thermocamera analysis

Characterization – Mechanical Test: SLSS coupons

Simplified Single Lap Shear Strength test, coupons manufactured with 4 plies stacked, isolating the load carrying area with Kapton film strips.

Test defined in: Dreher P, Chadwick AR, Nowotny S. Optimization of in-situ thermoplastic automated fiber placement process parameters through DoE. In: Proceedings of the 40th SAMPE Europe conference; 2019, p. 1–13.

Layup tool temperature effect:

Coupons manufactured varying the tool temperature.
NIP point affected by tool temperature.

Layup tool temperature [°C]	Nip point temperature (substrate) * [°C]	Crystallinity [%]	Shear Strength [MPa]
25	265	5.8	26.70±5.09
160	335	7.1	36.00±5.10
220	385	22.7	42.58±5.45

* Temperature measured at the substrate in the nip point area. The incoming tape was kept at a stable temperature of 350±15°C.

SLSS and DSC (crystallinity) results

Higher substrate temperature higher crystallinity and higher SLSS

Layup tool temperature effect:

Laser power is controlled to achieve a homogeneous nip point temperature.

Layup tool temperature [°C]	Nip point temperature* [°C]	Crystallinity [%]	Shear Strength [MPa]
25	330	5.8	31.11±4.85
160	350	7.0	30.00±3.37
220	360	26.5	28.67±1.77

* Temperature averaged from the substrate and the incoming tape in the nip point area.

SLSS and DSC (crystallinity) results

- ✓ Higher crystallinity doesn't mean higher SLSS.
- ✓ NIP Temperature influences in SLSS more.

LASER – NIP Temperature Control:

Relation between SLS strength and nip point temperature

Higher NIP temperature means higher SLSS

Above 400 °C, silicone rollers show thermal degradation

AFP roller. Left: roller without degradation.
Right: roller with degradation.

Spectrum	C	O	Si
A- 1	84.21	15.79	-
B- 1	73.21	26.79	-
B- 2	79.32	20.68	-
B- 3	87.84	12.16	-
C- 1	41.81	36.47	21.73
C- 2	87.82	12.18	-

SEM EDS (Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy) for surface silicon evaluation.

NIP Temperature and Compaction Force

100% = 6 bar.

Processing speed effect:

Void content at:

- ✓ NIP Temperature: 400 °C
- ✓ Speed: 250 mm/s
- ✓ Compaction Force: 6 bar

→ Degradation of compaction roller

Void content < 1% (4 layers)

Void content < 2% (with 27 layers)

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- ✓ CONCLUSIONS

On-going work:

Laser-based heating system for through-width-modulated temperature profile in AFP process

- During AFP process, instead of heating constant area, a **scanning laser** heat locally the tape.
- A thermal camera will control the heat delivered with a feedback loop: beam speed and/or intensity can locally accommodate bad heating performance.
- This will ensure that the tape always reach the desired temperature, allowing for improved performance.

Incoming cold tape
Beam heating the tape locally.
Intensity controlled based on thermal camera feedback
Junction with substrate

On-going work:

Laser-based heating system for through-width-modulated temperature profile in AFP process

Support

Light collimator

Fix optics

Steering mirror

On-going work:

Laser-based heating system for through-width-modulated temperature profile in AFP process

Energy profiles are sent to the tape and result successfully heating onto the tape.

On-going work:

Laser-based heating system for through-width-modulated temperature profile in AFP process

- The steering mirror and the laser intensity can be controlled directly with low electrical current (0-10V).
- According to the thermal camera, the tape is successfully heated up locally.
- Heating profiles can be tuned (more intensity in the center or in the edges)

On-going work:

Open-loop: sending predefined energy perfil and monitor heat evolution in time.

Temperature measurement on a metallic target, with a gaussian profile for intensity (request for more energy on the center and less on the edges).

Similar experiment with an inverted gaussian profile (more energy on the edges)

Close-loop control with fix energy profile: the profile is predefined and only its “base intensity” changes base on the thermal camera (one point measurement)

Evolution temperature top part (tape)

Evolution temperature substrate

Requested intensity profile

On-going work:

Laser-based heating system for through-width-modulated temperature profile in AFP process

- Intensity profile is dynamically calculated based on various measurement along the tape
- **Preliminary results:** Tape successfully heated = Good tape consolidation

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- There is a high influence of the layup tool temperature on crystallinity:
 - High tool temperatures (above the T_g of the polymer): high crystallinity percentages (around 25%) are obtained.
 - Tool temperatures below the T_g (147°C): high amorphous phase (below 10% crystallinity)
- NIP point control has high influence on SLSS values – higher NIP temperature higher SLSS.
- But.... above 400 °C, silicone rollers show thermal degradation.
- A scanning laser that heat locally the tape, instead of heating bigger and constant area, show promising results:
 - Tuned heating profile
 - Avoid roller degradation (more accurate heating)
- Future work: to develop an optimum scanning laser heating with feedback loop control.

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